

Origin of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution in Quantum Bound States

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April, 10, 2019

In a previous note (1), we argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) momentum distribution $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ in classical statistical mechanics follows from $P(p_1)P(p_2)=P(p_3)P(p_4)$ ((1)) (an “and” probability statement) and conservation of kinetic energy (elastic scattering). One takes the natural log of the former equation and equates it to the latter. It is also known that the MB distribution holds for the ground state quantum oscillator. In such a case, one does not have ((1)) because one has only one particle. Rather, the particle scatters with a potential, it seems. This begs the questions: What is the reaction equation analogous to ((1)) for the ground state oscillator? Does it also make use of a conservation equation for kinetic energy i.e. lack of information = $\ln(P(p))$ = kinetic energy? The objective of this note is to attempt to answer these questions. In particular, we find that: $f(k+j) f(k-j) = f_k^2 f_j^2$ and that $\ln(P(p))$ = kinetic energy. Calculations are performed in momentum space.

Statistical Mechanics

As noted above, the MB distribution follows from taking the log of $P(p_1)P(p_2)=P(p_3)P(p_4)$ ((1)) and equating it with a conservation of kinetic energy equation. In the language of information science, it seems that one is saying that $\ln(P(p))$ = lack of information = kinetic energy. If this is a general idea, it would be interesting to see if it holds in the case of quantum oscillator ground state which also has a momentum MB distribution.

Quantum Mechanics

Bound state quantum mechanics is based on the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((2))$$

Where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction = $\sum \text{over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)$ and E , the energy. Only a discrete set of E values satisfy ((2)). If one writes $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ each as a Fourier series and equates $\exp(ipx)$ terms, one arrives at:

$$\sum_{j+k=p} V_k f_j = (E - p^2/2m) f_p \quad ((3))$$

Interestingly, this suggests that in momentum space, one has a particle which may have a momentum of p at an instant. Since energy is conserved and there is only one particle, this suggests the potential energy at that instant is $E - p^2/2m$. Since one knows p , there is no information of x so one is speaking of a kind of average potential energy it seems. Now, at different times, different states f_j may scatter with the potential to create an $\exp(ipx)$. Given that they are interacting with the potential, this should represent a time-average potential energy

applicable to p . Equating the two yields ((3)), which is equivalent to the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

First, multiply both sides of ((3)) by $f(k-j)$. Then, it may be rewritten as:

$$\sum_k \psi_k \sum_j f(k+j) f(k-j)$$

$$\sum_k \psi_k \sum_j f(k+j) f(k-j) = \sum_k \sum_j (E - p^*p/2m) f_p^* f(k-j) \quad ((4))$$

Here $p^*p = (k+j)(k+j)$ and $f_p = f(k+j)$. Thus:

$$\sum_k \sum_j (E - p^*p/2m) f_p^* f(k-j) = \sum_{k,j} (E + k^*k/2m + j^*j/2m + kj/m) f(k+j)f(k-j)$$

For a fixed k , if $g(j) = g(-j)$ (which will be shown) then $\sum_j j^*k/m g(j) = 0$ so:

$$\sum_k \sum_j (E - p^*p/2m) f_p^* f(k-j) = \sum_{k,j} (E - j^*j/2m - k^*k/2m) f(k)f(k)g(j)$$

Consider a fixed k , which means one sums over j .

$$\text{Consider } \sum_j f(k+j) f(k-j) \quad ((5))$$

Is it possible to write this as $f(k)f(k) g(j)$ where $g(j)$ is a function of j ? If so, then both sides of ((4)) would have a similar symmetry, i.e. $\sum_k \psi_k f(k)f(k) \sum_j g(j) = \sum_{k,j} (E - j^*j/2m - k^*k/2m) f(k)f(k)g(j)$

$$\text{Thus, one seeks a solution: } \sum_j f(k+j) f(k-j) = f(k)f(k) g(j)$$

This problem seems very similar to a conservation of kinetic energy situation. Consider one term: $f(k+j)f(k-j) = f(k)f(k) g(j)$ ((6)). Conservation of kinetic energy gives:

$$(k+j)^2 + (k-j)^2 = 2k^2 + 2j^2 \quad ((7))$$

If one takes the natural log of ((6)), one obtains:

$$\ln[f(k+j)] + \ln[f(k-j)] = 2 \ln[f(k)] + \ln[g(j)] \quad ((8))$$

Comparing ((7)) and ((8)) leads to a solution:

$f(p) = \exp(-Cp^*p/2m)$ where C is a constant. The momentum probability $f_p^*f_p$ is also a Gaussian (MB) distribution. Thus, $g(j) = f(j) f(j)$.

Thus, in quantum mechanics (only for the case of the oscillator ground state, although that has not yet been established) it is possible to use the same ideas of equating a lack of information

In(f_p) to a kinetic energy just as in the classical statistical mechanics. The reaction equation, however, is not one of two particle scattering ((1)), but rather:

$$f(k+j) f(k-j) = f_k^2 f_j^2 \quad ((9))$$

A solution is $f(k) = C_1 \exp(-Ck^2/2m)$. It is interesting to note that the right hand side of ((9)) is identical to the right hand side of two particle scattering of classical statistical mechanics, but the left hand side is not. Note $f_k^2 f_j^2 = F(k)$ which is the probability to have momentum k . Physically, one does not have two particle scattering in the quantum case, but rather a particle scattering off a potential. It is interesting that both ((1)) and ((9)) yields MB distributions.

At this point, the above arguments have not demonstrated that the solution of ((9)) applies to the ground state of a quantum oscillator. Taking $f(k) = C_1 \exp(-Ck^2/2m)$ and inserting it into $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ yields $W(x) = C_1 \exp(-ax^2)$ which satisfies the ground state of a time-independent Schrodinger equation with $V(x) = 2ax^2$.

For cases other than the ground state of the oscillator, or for other potentials:

$$V_k \sum_j f(k+j)f(k-j) \text{ will not equal } f(k)f(k) f(j)f(j)$$

I.e. the $f(k+j)f(k-j)$ will not decouple. This leads to a complicated reaction structure which does not yield MB type statistics, but rather a new "quantum" type of internal statistics.

Considerations of Energy

Consider equation ((3)). At first glance, one might think there exists a solution for any energy. Assume an E which satisfies:

$$\sum_{k+j=p} V_k f_j = (E - p^2/2m) f_p \quad ((3))$$

Let $E \rightarrow E + dE$ and $f_p \rightarrow f_p + df_p$. Then, to first order:

$$\sum_{k+j=p} V_k df_j = (E - p^2/2m) df_p + f_p dE \text{ or}$$

$$\sum_{k+j=p} V_k [df_j - f_j dE / (E - p^2/2m)] = (E - p^2/2m) df_p \quad ((1))$$

The solution to this equation is already known, namely:

$df_p = a f_p$ where a is a tiny constant and:

$$[df_j - f_j dE / (E - p^2/2m)] = a f_j \text{ but } df_j = a f_j \text{ so } dE = 0.$$

Thus, it seems that if one has a solution for E in ((3)), one cannot find another solution by infinitesimally changing E . This idea of discrete energy levels E , however, is seen more clearly by studying the properties of the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in a previous note (1) we tried to argue that one could obtain the MB distribution by taking the natural log of a reaction equation, $P(p_1)P(p_2)=P(p_3)P(p_4)$ for classical statistical mechanics and equate it to a conservation of energy equation. It was suggested that a similar reaction equation should exist for quantum mechanics, together with a conservation of kinetic energy statement. In this note, we try to show that this reaction statement, which only holds for the ground state quantum oscillator is: $f(k+j) f(k-j) = f(k)^2 f(j)^2$. For other cases, $\sum_j f(k+j)f(k-j)$ does not decouple to give a function of k times a function of j and so argue that quantum mechanical bound states represent a more complicated statistical model than the Maxwell-Boltzmann case.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Independence and Time Reversal in Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Bound States (preprint, zenodo, 2019)